

Multilayer fire proof absorptive-insulative material composition with optimized parameters

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Abstract

Sound pollution, as of one of the main modern city irritations has become one of the paramount challenges of the current days. After COVID-19 outbreak many of the professional affairs concentrated at homes and residential areas. Many of the negotiations and conferences have been conducted at homes, where the noise level should be controlled. So, the proper addressing the problem, combining with the privilege of chemical composite synthesis is of great significance. In this paper a multilayer fire proof absorptive-insulator composite has been designed to control the acoustic parameters in residential areas. Apart from the desired acoustic parameters and inflammability, required in apartments, energy saving factors such as heat conductivity has also been optimized. The material has reached the absorption coefficient of 1, resulting in total sound absorption, and reasonable Sound Transmission Class (STC).

Keywords (Times New Roman bold 11 pt.): Multilayer Composite, Sound Absorption, Sound Transmission Class, Fire Proof absorber, Absorptive-Insulative, Acoustic Panel

1. Introduction

Noise pollution were soured up by industrial and cities development which reduces quality of life [1]. So, its reduction plays a very important role is one of the modern city necessities. The sound absorption and isolation are the main two steps of noise reduction procedure, which is mainly associated with porosity, pore size, density and thickness of the material [3]. Today, acoustic materials mainly include rock wool and glass wool as the principal ingredients, materials which are endangering human physical health [2]. In order to overcome this issue, polymer foams have synthetized recently, although they are expensive to use and cannot resist fire for a residential-required applications. Therefore, it is largely advisable to improve synthetic materials that not only are able to optimize acoustic parameters, but also is environmentally friendly and fire proof to be used in homes. This article presents a new approach toward acoustic composite panel structure with high inflammability aspect which, apart from reasonable acoustic insulation and absorption coefficients, has an optimized heath Conductivity coefficient, reduced flammability and Ability to resist the direct flame. thermal resistance was tested and calculated about 2.46 m². k/w, and conductivity coefficient is 0.0367

2. Materials and Methods

2-1. Materials:

The proposed acoustic panel is comprised of five different acoustic layers with different thicknesses which are high porous fiberglass- vinylacetate composite (2mm), Modified polyurethane foam (low density) (15mm, 10-30 kg/m³), basalt fiber (50mm, 80-120 kg/m³), Modified polyurethane foam (high density) (120-180 kg/m³), Polyvinilcoloride (3mm). Due to using variety of layers, consistent with desired acoustic parameters, this panel functions as both insulator and absorber. All the layers and their combination would meet the requirements of fire proof materials.

2-1-1- The preparation of foams

- **Low density polyurethane foam**

In order to produce low density polyurethane foam, the following materials were prepared:

1-Polyol polyurethane 2-Toluene diisocyanate 3-amine catalyst 4-tin catalyst 5- distilled water 6-silicone oil

These materials were industrial grade without any modification. To achieve a particular density formula of foam, it was tested about 150 times. Detailed information and the final result of these analyzes are at the disposal of the juridical personality of Mobtakeran Avaye Pad Company. however To produce foam with a density of Ƴ0 Kg/m³ materials was weighed according to the below table:

Table 1- low density foam

Materials	Weight (g)
Polyol polyurethane	2000
Toluene diisocyanate	1000
amine catalyst	1.6
tin catalyst	3.6
distilled water	140
silicone oil	17.6

First, polyurethane polyol, amine catalyst, tin catalyst, distilled water, silicone oil were mixed together and stirred with the Agitator at 2000 rpm for 5 minutes. Without stopping the stirring, TDI was added to the above composition. It should be noted that as soon as TDI is added, the reaction begins to progress. After adding TDI, continue mixing for another 10 seconds and then transfer the resulting mixture in a mold of 65 cm by 65 cm by 100 cm. The ambient temperature was kept at 30 ° C. Two hours later, remove the formed foam from the mold and leave it in the open air for 24 hours to dry completely. The final foam is cut into 60 x 60 x 1 cm plates.

- **Fire retardant additive**

In order to fire-retardants the foam, the following mixture was created:

Table 2 - high density foam

materials	Weight (g)
Vinyl acetate homopolymer	1000
monoammonium phosphate	200
Pentaerythritol	180
Chlorinated paraffins	210
Stabilizer	50

Distilled water	100
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All materials were industrial grade and all powders were milled by 1000 mesh. The above ingredients were mixed together and stirred for 10 minutes to obtain a perfectly homogeneous solution. The resulting solution was sprayed on the foam prepared from the previous step. The wet foam is transferred to a drying room at 50 ° C and left there for 8 hours. The obtained product is ready for use in the acoustic panel.

- **The preparation of final acoustic panel:**

In order to achieve high density foam for the rear layers of the acoustic panel, the materials are prepared according to the following table.

Table 3 - final panel structure

Materials	Weight (g)
Polyol polyurethane	100
Toluene diisocyanate	50
amine catalyst	0.95
tin catalyst	1.79
distilled water	13
silicone oil	1.2
monoammonium phosphate	15
Pentaerythritol	13.5
Chlorinated paraffins	15
Stabilizer	3

All materials are industrial grade and the powders were ground by 1000 mesh. In another container, all the above-mentioned ingredients except TDI were mixed together for 5 minutes and 2000 rpm. After that, TDI was added to the stirred mixture and stirring continues for another 10 seconds. The resulting material was poured into a hollow cubic polyvinyl chloride mold with dimensional 60*60*7 cm with 1.6 cm thickness and basalt mineral fibers with dimensional 56.8*56.8*5 cm were immediately placed on it. This action has caused the foam to don't increase in volume and its density remains high. After 15 minutes, the gap between the mold and the mineral fibers is filled with high density fireproof foam.

The low-density foam that was explained earlier was placed on the mineral fibers. The entire composition is sealed by glass fibers and modified polyacrylic resin is sprayed on it. Finally, the panel is transferred to the drying room with a temperature of 50 degrees Celsius for 4 hours and the final panel is formed.

2-2. Methods:

Different examination had been tested to indicate high quality of hybrid panels.

2-2-1. Conductivity coefficient test

thermal resistance of the product is calculated by using The Iranian National Standard No. 8621. The device has a heater at the top of the test, two thermometers and a cooling unit at the bottom of the test, which declares a constant, uniform heat flow. The specimen is placed between hot and cold plates and the flow direction is from top to bottom.

2-2-1. Flammability test

The samples are exposed to the flame for 20 minutes. This test is used to evaluate the fire response of non-flooring building materials that are subject to heat attack by a single ignited unit. ISO11925-2, EN13823, EN13501-1 have used in this test. The specimens were formed an edge which has showed in fig... then introduced to poly propane torch from front bottom.

2-2-3. Ability to ignite in direct contact with the flame test

ISO11925-2 (7271-4 Iranian national standard) are used to evaluate ability to ignite. Flame was contact to specimen for 15 seconds in humidity 22% and 24 degree Celsius.

3- Results and discussions:

3-1. Mechanisms:

3-1-1. Fire resistant mechanism:

After reaching the flame, monoammonium phosphate melts at 215 ° C and the following reaction occurs at 238 ° C:

At slightly higher temperatures, the acid formed reacts with pentaerythritol to esterify the polyhydric compound. This reaction is shown in the following equation:

By changing the temperature mentioned in the first step and during esterification, the binder melts to some extent. Between 280 and 350 ° C, the

phosphoric ester decomposes according to the following equation and the bonds are broken, leaving acid, water and carbon:

At the same time, a reaction occurs according to the following equation, where the output of its compounds are gases such as hydrogen chloride and hydrochloric acid that will swell the molten mass.

The adhesive resin softens and forms a thin layer on the mixture that prevents the dispersion of gases. As the temperature increases, the density of the insole material increases. Due to intermolecular bonding and carbonization, the foam formed solidifies to form a highly porous material. At temperatures above 600 ° C, thermal decomposition or oxidation of the carbonized mass will occur. Compared to the initial thickness, the inlet layer is about 50 to 100 times larger and creates a thermal barrier that protects the substrate from the effects of heat and decomposition.

3-1-2. Sound absorption and transmission mechanisms:

To form a reliable acoustic panel which could serve as both insulator and absorber at the broadband-frequency range, composition of different layers with consistent characters are required. [5] this panel would perform insulation regarding the outer layers and absorption using inner layers' characteristics. The main parameter associated with insulation is material's density. When the sound waves in a certain environment hits the material with a very different mass level, it tends to reflect with proportion to mass difference. Therefore, the higher the difference the higher the reflection and lower the transmission. this is the main reason that materials such as concrete are categorized as a very well-known insulator. [7] higher insulation would necessarily mean a higher reverberation time. So, the remained energy of the sound must be damped using absorption approaches.

Two outer layers of the panel have extremely high density in comparison with air. So, it functions as a very good insulator, which is presented in the Sound Transmission Class STC result section of this paper. Materials usually exploit three different absorption mechanisms in different frequency bandwidth ranges. High frequencies are usually absorbed by the fictitious interaction of moving air particle inside the materials holes. Therefore, higher porous density materials with smaller holes would play a significant role in high frequency absorption. [6] the effective

absorption frequency is proportional to number of holes and reversed to the radius of holes. [4]

Second mechanism uses a plate reverberator to decrease sound wave energy by transforming it into a mechanical, which will be later diminished in the air. The main absorption frequency depends on the thickness and the density of the material. [7]

Third absorption mechanism mainly works on the bass frequency range. This would utilize the amplified sound deterioration caused by the standing waves inside a volume. [8]

The presented material, which is called a broadband absorber, uses all three mechanisms to cover a wide range frequency absorption.

3-2. Sound analysis:

3-2-1. Sound absorption analysis:

as discussed in the previous section, the presented structure is designed to perform a reasonable function through a wide range of frequency. Therefore, it includes a porous material in front, to absorb higher frequencies and then two deliberately different vibrating materials with different density and thickness to cover a wider mid and bass range of frequencies. As a result, the proposed structure would reach the absorption coefficient of 1 for the frequencies over 125Hz, as shown in figure 1. Experiments have been conducted in consistency with Iranian national standard No.10945 and No.8184. the reason that the graph spikes over 1 is that in the experiments, the area effective is approximately calculated and it definitely includes error. In order to address this issue a weighing parameter is applied to the graph, resulting in figure 2.

Figure 1 - sound absorption coefficient

Figure 2 - weighted sound absorption coefficient

3-2-2. Sound transmission class (STC) analysis:

Sound Transmission Class (STC) is the parameter describing the insulation level of a material. It uses the transmission index in 24 different audible frequencies among 128Hz to 4096Hz to classify different materials. The rating STC would be over 35 in bass frequencies and it reaches 65 in higher frequencies.

Figure 3 - STC of the wall with and without the acoustic panel

3-3. Fire resistance analysis:

The specimen introduced to fire at 300th second. smoke discharges were observed at 345th second, which means that there were 45 seconds of complete fire resistance in the panels. Then at 360th second, the surface of the panels was burnt. The fire spreads upward and no side spreading was observed. Fig ... were taken during the Fire resistance test which describe the direction of spreading the fire. At 367th second, the fire spreads through gaps between panels which will help the fire to spread through hollow canal between panels. The panel surface began to

disform and expand in the 390th second. Finally, the panels were resisted till 512th second and chard completely but the remaining panels were stand firmly to the structure which means that the panels were not turned into ashes which can clearly see in fig 4 which was showed the panels.

Figure 4 - absorber panels during fire resistance test

Figure 5 - absorbing panel after and before the fire resistance test

3-4. Heat Release Rate (HRR):

HRR demonstrate the heat release rate of the specimens. HRR increases is a result of heat release increasing which means either there is a heat source or the materials are fired.

The HRR diagrams were shown in figure 6 in the 300th second, the fire introduced to the panels, as fig (6) suggests that, the HRR increased till 400th second. During this period, the surface of the panels was ignited and were begun to firing. At 400th second, the panel temperature was reached 215 ° C and fire extinguishing process were initiated. From 400th second till 512th second, fire resistance process continued and at 512th second, the barrier between panel and fire source was formed, which results in preventing fire penetration through this barrier so the panel were stay firm on the structure and stabled as mentioned above.

Figure 6 - HRR Diagram of Soundphix panels

3-5.Total heat release (THR) & fire growth rate (FIGRA):

The THR and FIGRA diagram is showed in fig (.). The red diagram shows FIGRA and black diagram shows THR. At 300th second, with the igniting the burner, FIGRA which indicates the growth rate of fire, went up to 7 M.J which demonstrated the fire initiation. After short period of time (about 10 second), the fire-resistant mechanism triggered and consumed the fire heat to initiate its reactions so the fire growth rate plunged dramatically since at second 512th, the barrier would form and prevent fire from penetrating the panel. Same phenomenon happened to THR which indicates the total heat releases during fire process. At second 300th, the burner started to firing and the total heat increased rapidly. As the barrier formed, the slop of THR was fixed which represented the burner heat generation.

Figure 7 - THR and FIGRA of Soundphix panel

3-6.Smoke growth rate (SMOGRA) and total smoke production (TSP):

Smoke growth rate and total smoke production is showed in fig (7). In the fire-resistant process there was some smoke due to their reactions which would be NH₃ and after the barrier formation, there were not any smoke generation which express the preventing of the barrier from fire penetration.

4- Conclusion:

The proposed multilayer composite structure would address sound pollution, one of the significant modern city irritations as being both the reasonable insulator and a broadband absorber. The density and thickness match results in a roughly flat frequency absorption response. The absorption coefficient reach 1 over a certain frequency, meaning that It would absorb any sound wave hitting the material over that frequency. So, the material would be classified as perfect partition cover in residential areas. In addition, the additives have rendered the material inflammable and fire resistant, the characteristics essential to modern apartments. Also, the Soundphix broadband absorber panels could form a barrier through fire which cause to preventing fire from reaching the inner parts which could protect the main panel and environs furniture from fire spreading.

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